

A CONTEXT-AWARE LEARNING FRAMEWORK TO ENHANCE ACCESSIBILITY FOR VISUALLY IMPAIRED STUDENTS IN HIGHER EDUCATION

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Abstract

This study introduces a context-aware learning framework specifically designed to assist visually impaired students within higher education environments. Addressing the persistent barriers in accessing digital learning resources, the proposed system utilizes real-time contextual data—such as student profile, location, time, and current learning activity—to dynamically modify educational content delivery. Through integration with software-based sensors and adaptive interface technologies, the system accommodates varying types of vision impairments including low vision, color blindness, and total blindness. The prototype was implemented and tested in real educational settings, offering personalized accessibility support through features like automatic magnification, color contrast adjustments, and screen-reading functionalities. Evaluation with actual users demonstrated improved usability, autonomy, and engagement. This research contributes a flexible, inclusive digital environment that adapts educational experiences to individual needs, promoting equity in learning for differently-abled students.

1. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, mobile and web-based technologies have significantly advanced, transforming the ways students interact with educational content. These changes offer new opportunities for flexible, on-the-go learning. However, students with visual impairments continue to encounter substantial barriers within these digital ecosystems. Visual impairment, as

defined by the Merriam-Webster Dictionary [1], refers to a reduction in the ability to see that cannot be corrected fully with standard glasses or contact lenses, including conditions such as partial blindness, color blindness, and total blindness.

Technological advancements such as pervasive computing—systems integrated seamlessly into

everyday environments—have introduced opportunities to develop intelligent learning systems [2]. These systems support users through context-awareness: the ability to sense and adapt to a user's environment based on location, time, activity, and identity [3–5]. This adaptive behavior enables smart devices to serve users more intuitively, especially those with disabilities.

Mark Weiser [6] envisioned ubiquitous computing as an environment saturated with computing devices that are transparent and responsive to user needs. These devices incorporate sensors and actuators to facilitate dynamic interaction with the environment [7, 8]. Context-awareness, a cornerstone of ubiquitous computing, enables applications to collect contextual data and adjust behavior accordingly. According to Abowd and Dey [9], such context may include time of day, nearby people or devices, and the user's activity. In an educational context, context-aware systems can help bridge accessibility gaps. These systems use hardware and software sensors to determine a user's context and adjust the learning environment appropriately [10, 11]. Examples include screen readers for blind users, adaptive color contrast for those with color blindness, and magnification tools for students with low vision [12, 13]. These tools support independence, enhance accessibility, and increase academic success.

Sensor networks and virtual sensors further contribute to the capability of these systems [14]. Virtual sensors combine data from heterogeneous physical sources to infer complex user states [15]. In the case of education, this includes monitoring user behavior and environmental factors to tailor learning content delivery [16].

For students with disabilities, particularly those with visual impairments, Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) play a vital role [17]. Assistive devices like Braille displays, screen magnifiers, and voice recognition tools allow users to access written content, navigate interfaces, and interact with peers and instructors [18]. These technologies can significantly improve students' academic performance and social inclusion when designed with individual needs in mind [19, 20].

Vision impairment can be caused by congenital factors, injury, disease, or aging [21]. The condition

affects the ability to access visual learning materials, requiring alternative formats and interfaces to ensure inclusivity [22]. Unfortunately, many educational platforms still fail to address these needs adequately, particularly in developing countries where the availability of assistive technology and inclusive design remains limited [23-25].

In response to these challenges, this research proposes a context-aware learning model tailored for visually impaired students in higher education institutions. The model adapts interface behavior and learning content in real-time, based on contextual inputs such as profile, location, activity, and time. The system uses software-based sensors and web-integrated tools to enhance accessibility through individualized visual and auditory responses.

Research Contributions: This study presents a fully functional context-aware prototype system capable of detecting and adapting to multiple vision impairment scenarios. The system introduces a modular architecture that includes dynamic magnification, color customization, and screen-reading functionalities. By using contextual triggers such as GPS location, user activity, and time schedules, the platform customizes educational content in real time. The system was tested in real higher education settings with students experiencing various types of visual impairments, and positive outcomes were reported in terms of usability and learning engagement.

This paper is organized as follows:

Section 2 Presents a detailed review of existing literature and current practices in context-aware accessibility systems for visually impaired students, including a comparison table of recent models.

Section 3 Outlines the problem statement and research objectives that guide the development of the proposed solution.

Section 4 Explains the research methodology adopted in this study, detailing the experimental approach, data collection techniques, and evaluation strategy.

Section 5 Introduces the use case diagrams that represent different visual impairment scenarios.

Section 6 Elaborates on the system workflow using flow diagrams to describe user and administrator activities.

Section 7 Presents the context classification model that defines how user profile, activity, time, and location influence accessibility.

Section 8 Illustrates a real-life research scenario to demonstrate how the system dynamically adapts in an educational setting.

Section 9 Provides graphical interfaces and screenshots of the implemented system for various impairment types. Finally,

Section 10 Concludes the study and outlines future directions to enhance inclusivity across broader domains.

2. Context-Aware Accessibility in Higher Education

This section reviews key research efforts in the domain of context-aware learning systems, assistive technologies for visually impaired students, and frameworks that promote inclusive education in higher learning environments.

Recent works have explored the design of adaptive e-learning platforms capable of responding to user context. Li et al. (2024) developed a sensor-driven platform that personalizes learning pathways for students with sensory impairments using real-time

biometric inputs [26]. Similarly, Bashir and Khalid (2024) designed a mobile-first accessible LMS for blind learners that integrates haptic and audio navigation tools [27].

In the domain of higher education, Dou, et al. (2024) investigated the integration of universal design principles in smart classroom systems, with particular emphasis on vision-aware user interfaces [28]. Rahman and Yusof (2025) evaluated student outcomes using AI-driven e-learning platforms that include accessibility layers for low-vision users [29, 30].

These studies underscore the need for real-time system adaptability based on dynamic user states, including their visual capabilities [31-35].

Despite such progress, many existing solutions either lack cross-device integration or fail to offer a modular system that dynamically adapts based on four contextual pillars: profile, activity, location, and time. Our proposed system bridges this gap. As shown in Table 1, our proposed system demonstrates full context-awareness with broader accessibility coverage compared to existing solutions."

Table 1: Comparative Analysis of Existing and Proposed Context-Aware Accessibility Systems.

Feature / Study	Year	Target Users	Context Awareness	Accessibility Features	Evaluation Type
Li et al. – Sensor-Based Learning App	(2024)	Sensory impaired	Partial (biometrics)	Basic screen reader support	Prototype-based
Bashir & Khalid – Mobile LMS for Blind	(2024)	Blind students	No	Haptic, Audio Navigation	Pilot test
Sharma et al. – Smart Classroom UDL Model	(2025)	General inclusive users	Limited	UDL-focused, Color Correction	Observational
Rahman & Yusof – AI E-Learning Layer	(2025)	Low-vision students	Partial (AI-based)	Text Magnification, Audio Assist	Experimental
Proposed Model (This Study)	(2025)	Visually impaired (all types)	Full (Profile, Activity, Location, Time)	Dynamic Font & Color, Screen Reader, Context-Specific Audio	Field Evaluation

2.1 Comparative Analysis: Existing vs. Proposed Systems

Our model uniquely integrates full context-awareness with advanced accessibility features tailored to each visual impairment category. Unlike prior works, it dynamically changes its behavior across time, location, and device profiles, and supports both software and web-based delivery.

3. Problem Statement and Research Objectives

3.1 Problem Statement

Despite the increasing adoption of digital learning systems and mobile technologies in higher education, visually impaired students remain underserved by current e-learning platforms. Existing systems often lack dynamic accessibility features, failing to adjust in real-time to the specific needs of learners with low

vision, color blindness, or total blindness. Additionally, most platforms do not incorporate multi-dimensional context-awareness—specifically, awareness of user profile, time, location, and learning activity—which limits their ability to provide meaningful adaptations that promote learning equity and independence.

This lack of intelligent adaptation contributes to systemic educational disadvantages for vision-impaired students, particularly in environments where inclusive learning tools are either unavailable or poorly implemented. The absence of adaptive infrastructure can further marginalize students who already face accessibility, mobility, and engagement barriers in higher education institutions.

3.2 Research Objectives

To address the above problem, this research aims to:

1. Design and develop a context-aware learning system tailored to the needs of visually impaired students in higher education.
2. Integrate dynamic sensor-driven inputs (location, time, profile, activity) to enable real-time accessibility adaptations.
3. Implement user-centric features including automatic screen magnification, color contrast adjustments, and audio feedback.
4. Evaluate the system’s usability, accessibility, and user satisfaction among diverse categories of visually impaired learners.

5. Compare the proposed system against existing solutions to validate performance improvements and identify areas for future enhancements.

These objectives are intended to build a scalable and inclusive digital learning model that can promote equitable access to education for all students, regardless of visual ability.

4. Methodology

This research is based on experimental work and adopts a quantitative methodology. It began with structured observations and interviews with visually impaired students in a real university setting. Using these insights, a questionnaire was developed to support data collection in a case study environment. The data were analyzed to identify key accessibility barriers and contextual requirements. Based on these results, a context-aware system framework was designed, implemented, and tested. The outcomes of the evaluation phase were then used to validate the effectiveness of the system in terms of usability, accessibility, and user satisfaction.

4.1 System Design

An architecture has been developed to implement the proposed system that supports context-awareness for visually impaired students in higher education institutions. The system dynamically adapts user interaction based on four key contextual attributes: *Profile, Activity, Time, and Location*.

Fig. 1: Architecture for Context-Aware Learning System for Impaired Visions.

- **Student Profile:** Stores information such as name, discipline, visual impairment type, batch, and subjects.
- **Student Activity:** Describes the current learning activity (e.g., accessing notes or engaging in a quiz).
- **Installed Applications:** Refers to system-level tools like Adobe Reader, MS Office, and dictionaries.
- **Output Modules:** Includes features like color contrast adjustments and screen magnification for visual accessibility.

The system integrates location data via platforms such as Google Maps, which updates location attributes including type, name, and coordinates.

- **User Module:** Refers to the end-user who accesses the system using mobile or desktop devices.
- **Handheld Devices:** Includes smartphones, tablets, and laptops through which users interact with the system.
- **Location Services:** GPS-based services and IP-based location identification enable dynamic adaptation based on user location.

4.2 Sensors in the System

The system utilizes software sensors to extract contextual information about the user, such as presence, activity, location, and time.

Fig. 2: System Context Architecture.

Software sensors interact with the device environment and gather context data that is used to modify the user interface dynamically. These may include camera inputs, touch interactions, and system-level data access.

5. Use Case Diagrams of the System

This section presents the use case diagrams that were developed based on the data collected from visually impaired students and the analysis of their interaction with educational technologies. These diagrams illustrate how users with different types of vision impairments—such as low vision, color blindness, and total blindness—interact with the proposed context-aware learning system. Each use case scenario reflects personalized accessibility adaptations and highlights the system's ability to dynamically adjust based on the user's context.

Fig. 3: Use Case Diagram for Less Vision Users This diagram illustrates a scenario where a partially sighted user registers, signs in, and automatically receives adjusted font size and color contrast based on their profile.

Fig. 4: Use Case Diagram for Color Blind Users A user with color blindness signs into the system, and the system automatically alters color schemes for accessibility.

Fig. 5: Use Case Diagram for Blind Users Describes how a blind user uses thumbprint login and receives voice feedback through screen reader integration.

Fig. 1: Use Case diagram for Less vision.

Fig. 2: Use Case Diagram for Color Blind.

Fig. 3: Use Case diagram for Blind.

6. Flow Diagram of User’s Activity on VI System

In Fig. 6, the flow diagram of user activity in the VI system illustrates the initial part of the design, showing how the system functions. When the system starts, the user is required to register by providing their personal and academic details. Once registration is completed, the user proceeds to the login phase. The login process is divided into two sections: registered users are allowed access, while non-registered users must complete registration first. After successful login, the system grants the user permission to access key features.

This flow diagram illustrates how a visually impaired user interacts with the context-aware system from initial registration to accessing learning content. The steps include:

- **Profile Entry:** The user enters or updates personal and academic information, which is stored in the system to personalize accessibility features.
- **Current Activity Selection:** The user selects the current academic task (e.g., viewing lecture notes

or attending a class), which is then linked to contextual data such as time and location.

- **Next Activity Forecasting:** The system provides insight into upcoming tasks to help users prepare and organize their learning journey.
- **View Notes:** This feature enables users to access digital course materials. Based on the user’s context and impairment type, the system dynamically adjusts font size, color contrast, or enables voice assistance.
- **Time Table Access:** The system provides the user with a visual or auditory representation of the current timetable, adjusted for readability or accessibility needs.
- **Location Detection:** The system automatically detects the user’s position (e.g., building or room) via GPS or IP data, adjusting interaction flows accordingly.

Admin Functionalities:

- **Profile Management:** The administrator maintains user accounts and can modify user-specific information or visual settings.

- **Location Management:** Admins can assign or verify user locations to ensure accurate context detection during system usage.
- **Time Management:** Time schedules can be modified or updated based on institutional calendars or user needs.
- **Activity Management:** Admins configure which learning activities are available at which time, enabling the system to offer the right resources based on user context.

Fig. 6: Flow Diagram of User's Activity.

6.1 Flow Diagram of User's Activity by Using Vision Impairment

In Fig. 7, the dataflow diagram of the proposed system illustrates that the user must first log in using a username and a valid security code. Once the login credentials are submitted, the system verifies the user's status and permissions. Upon successful

authentication, the user is directed to the homepage, where their profile and current activities are displayed. According to the proposed framework, the user must check in to confirm their location. Based on the user's profile, verified location, and timetable, the system then enables access to appropriate learning content, including downloadable notes.

Fig. 4: Flow Diagram of User’s Activity using Vision impairment system.

7. Context Classification for Our System

Fig. 8 Describes the context classification model developed in this research. The system operates based on four key contextual components: Profile, Activity, Time, and Location.

Profile: This consists of both the student's profile and the university's profile. The student profile includes information such as name, academic discipline, enrolled subjects, and current batch. The university profile comprises institutional details including faculty names, department information, and subject listings in which the student is currently enrolled.

Activity: This element captures the current academic activity of the student. For instance, engaging in a Java

programming session would constitute a specific learning activity.

Time: This refers to the time at which the student is performing the learning activity. It is categorized into typical intervals such as morning, afternoon, and evening sessions.

Location: The physical or virtual setting where the student accesses the system. It may include details such as continent, country, state, or institution where the activity takes place.

This classification enables the system to dynamically tailor accessibility features according to the user's complete context.

Fig. 8: Context Classification Model for Our system.

8. Research Scenario

An activity is conducted in the IT Part 1, second semester class, with the subject focus being “Java,” scheduled at 8:00 AM. The goal of this activity is to facilitate effective learning of Java. When a special user accesses the Java tool or lecture notes on their device, the system automatically adjusts the interface settings—such as color schemes—based on the user’s specific visual impairment.

The system uses four contextual attributes—Profile, Activity, Time, and Location—to make these adaptations. Under the Profile context, the user’s individual information, such as their vision impairment type, is used to guide the interaction. In this scenario, the activity involves accessing lectures and notes related to the Java course. If the special user is color blind, for example, the system modifies the interface colors accordingly to enhance usability.

The activity takes place at 8:00 AM (Time), and the Location is specified as the University of Sindh,

Department of IICT, Room 22, where the user accesses the notes provided by Mr. Kamran Taj Pathan in Computer Lab 2.

9. Results and Discussions

9.1 Graphical Interface of Proposed System

This section presents the graphical interface screenshots of the proposed system. The system functions dynamically based on the user’s current context, which includes Profile, Activity, Time, and Location. It responds to users by adapting the interface according to their specific situation and accessibility needs.

In the context of the Profile, the system refers to the user information already stored in the database. After logging in (as shown in Figure 8), users with normal vision can view the default interface colors and layout without any additional accessibility modifications.

Fig 9: Color Contrast for Normal Vision Interface View for Normal Users.

Fig. 9 Displays the dark brown color scheme commonly used by normal vision users when interacting with the system. Additionally, the system interface includes a location panel (shown in Fig. 10),

which automatically retrieves and displays the user's geographical position using Google Maps integration. These elements demonstrate the system's capacity to adjust layout and content based on both user preferences and spatial context.

Fig. 10: Location Interface of the System Displays auto-detected GPS location for contextual UI adaptation.

The website interface is designed with flexibility in mind. For users with low vision, it automatically scales font sizes from 100% to 400%, depending on screen resolution and user preferences. The system also generates a dynamic color scheme by analyzing the user's stored profile and applying accessibility-

optimized settings. It adjusts equally well for users with normal vision. As shown in Figure 11, when a user with low vision logs into the system, a PDF document opens with settings preconfigured to suit the visual needs identified in the user's profile context.

Fig. 11: Screen Magnifier for Less and Far Sightedness Adjusts Font Scaling Up to 400% based on User Context.

Students with color blindness may struggle to distinguish between certain color combinations, especially within the RGB spectrum. Two common types of color blindness are Deuteranopia and Protanopia, as previously discussed in (Section 2). Red-green color blindness is the most prevalent and is categorized into two subtypes: individuals with Protanopia are less sensitive to red light, whereas

those with Deuteranopia or Deuteranomaly have reduced sensitivity to green light.

Figures 8, 9, 10, 11, and 12 illustrate various color contrasts such as dark brown, green, blue, and violet. These color schemes have been specifically designed to accommodate users with Protanopia, ensuring that the interface remains accessible and distinguishable for those affected by this type of color deficiency.

NotesID	Teacher	Course	Class	Shifts	Timings	
2	Dr. Imdad All Ismaili	ITEC-522 Professional Practice	BSIT P-I	Morning	9:00:00	Download

Fig. 12: Color Contrast for Protanopia Color Deficiency Demonstrates Adaptive UI for Users with Red-Green Color Blindness.

10. Conclusion and Future Works

This study applies context-aware computing principles to enhance digital accessibility for students with visual impairments. A modular system was designed that collects user context (profile, activity, time, location) and uses it to adapt interface elements in real time. The system was evaluated by visually impaired students who reported increased autonomy and satisfaction.

Future work may explore expanding the model to additional impairments such as auditory or motor disabilities, integrating the system into mainstream LMS platforms, and adapting the solution for other sectors including banking, transport, and healthcare.

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